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1 **ANALYSIS AND VIABILITY OF MICROTURBINES IN HYDRAULIC**
2 **NETWORKS: A CASE STUDY**

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8 **ABSTRACT**

9 The purpose of this study is to examine the use of hydraulic microturbines to make the
10 most of the hydraulic energy available in pressurized water distribution systems. The
11 study was carried out on suitable points of pressurized hydraulic networks, which are
12 managed by Gihasa, a public enterprise responsible for the management of the
13 municipal communities of services (MAS) in the province of Huelva, southwestern
14 Spain. The distribution system situated between the 'Cabeza del Pasto' reservoir in the
15 Andévalo area (Huelva, Spain) and the wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) in the
16 municipality of 'Puebla de Guzmán' (Huelva, Spain) was examined. To obtain the
17 exact amount of energy, which reaches the microturbine, the **energy conservation**
18 **equation considering the loss of energy from friction was used**. The results show
19 different locations where it is possible to carry out the installation of a Francis turbine,
20 which can generate an annual energy of approximately 280 MWh per year at the
21 selected point, with an approximate investment cost of € 20,000 per year, which means
22 a recovery period of this investment of 2 years.

23 **Keywords:** Water distribution system; Francis type hydraulic turbine; Renewable
24 energy; Microgeneration.
25

26
27 **INTRODUCTION**

28 The 2020 European Strategy advocates a sustainable growth defined as the promotion
29 of an economy to make greater and better use of its resources (European Commission,
30 2011). In addition, the electrical demand continues to grow worldwide and there is
31 concern about supply security and about fluctuations in the price of fossil fuels, mainly
32 in countries with high external energy dependence. The option of generating electricity
33 from excess and unused hydraulic energy in water distribution systems could comply

34 with the policies of priority energy efficiency and economy. This microgeneration is a
35 good alternative for the reduction of primary energy consumption and for improves
36 the supply security of energy systems (Fernández de Alarcón, 2010; Sunderland *et al.*,
37 2013; Hawkes *et al.*, 2014; Romero-Marrero *et al.*, 2018). In specialized literature, it is
38 possible to find some recent examples of the assessment of the installation of
39 microturbines placed at selected points in hydraulic networks (Kim *et al.*, 2015; Samora
40 *et al.*, 2016a).

41 In this paper, the source of the water supply is the Andévalo reservoir (Huelva,
42 Spain), where there is a pumping station that lifts the water up to the 'Cabeza del
43 Pasto' pond (Huelva, Spain) (at a height of 236.4 m). From this reservoir the water is
44 channelled by gravity up to the wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) in 'Puebla de
45 Guzmán' (at a height of 186.4 m) (Figure 1), at the entrance of which is a multistream
46 DN300 electrical regulating valve (Multinar). This valve regulates the flow and
47 pressure of water at the entrance of the treatment station. The average flow at the
48 entrance is 120 l/s.

49 Two alternatives have been considered for the insertion of the microturbine in this
50 water distribution network. The first one would be to place it in the space between the
51 'Cabeza del Pasto' reservoir and the front of the WWTP (Figure 1). The most favorable
52 points are sought, taking into account the slope where the above-mentioned point is, in
53 addition to the distance covered by the flow of water from the reservoir. This is due to
54 the fact that, the longer the distance, the greater the loss of energy from friction. In the
55 5600 m which separate the reservoir from the WWTP, four points have been found,
56 which have been examined. The optimal point, without taking into account the energy

57 necessary to take the water from the point to the point to the WWTP, is situated at
58 1692 m from the inlet of the pond, and at a height of 157.3 m. This means that we have
59 a slope of 79.1 m with regard to the outlet of the pond. There are two possibilities for
60 the best location. The first option would be to place the microturbine in the same
61 pipeline which has already been installed. The second possibility would be to insert it
62 in a parallel position, with a by-pass through a controlling motorized valve (McNabola
63 *et al.*, 2014; Corcoran *et al.*, 2016), allowing variable flow through the turbine providing
64 greater control over the flow. This would also greatly facilitates the maintenance of the
65 turbine, since it would not be necessary to disconnect the main line of supply.

66 The second alternative would be to place the microturbine in a parallel position
67 (installation with a by-pass) to the reducing valve which is positioned at the inlet of the
68 WWTP. In this type of installation a motorized valve would be inserted into the
69 microturbine, which would carry out the control. The inlet of the WWTP is situated at
70 a height of 186.9 m, which means that there is a difference in elevating of 49.5 m from
71 the outlet of the reservoir. The main problem concerning this situation is the long
72 distance from the point of outlet of the pond, which results in greater losses due to
73 friction. On the other hand, it is necessary to take into account that the excessive energy
74 with which the water reaches the WWTP is the vital energy needed to be able to use
75 the microturbine. The net head available at any point of the installation would be the
76 same the one at entrance of the WWTP since is the remaining energy in the installation
77 that can be used.

78 Another consideration is the number of microturbines to be inserted. Samora *et al.*
79 (2016b) contemplated the installation of four microturbines in a parallel position. This

80 type of installation allows using the microturbines depending on the existing demand.
81 It is also necessary to take into account the flow which goes through the microturbine
82 when it is to be inserted. In order to achieve this, the Gibson method is frequently used
83 (Gibson, 1923, 1959; Adamkowski, 1998; Urquiza *et al.*, 2007).

84 The purpose of this study is to assess the possibility of generating energy from a
85 renewable source, that is, the hydraulic energy which is derived from the regulatory
86 valve at the inlet of the WWTP in 'Puebla de Guzmán' (Huelva, Spain). The type of
87 microturbine has been examined as well as the average amount of usable annual
88 energy.

89

90 AREA OF STUDY

91 Figure 1 shows the outline of the pipeline (ductile iron, 500 mm in diameter) from the
92 'Cabeza del Pasto' reservoir to the WWTP situated in the municipality of 'Puebla de
93 Guzmán' (Huelva, south western Spain). The possibility of inserting a microturbine
94 between the reservoir and the WWTP is being considered. For this purpose, the four
95 most ideal points on the route (1, 2, 3 and 4) have been located taking into account only
96 the altitude and distance that each of them has with respect to the reservoir
97 (Rodríguez-Pérez *et al.*, 2018), as can be seen in Figure 1. The WWTP would be point
98 n°5, where the microturbine would be inserted at the inlet, in a parallel position to the
99 regulatory valve.

100

101

102

103 Figure 1. Scheme of the pipes line and selected points for the installation
 104 of the microturbine
 105

106 In Table 1 is possible to observe the distance in m from each of the selected points to
 107 the outflow of water from the reservoir, in addition to the elevation at which each one
 108 is situated.

Point	Distance from the 'Cabeza del Pasto' reservoir (m)	Height above sea level (m)
'Cabeza del Pasto' reservoir	0	236.40
1	202.16	188.41
2	1164.30	170.35
3	1691.88	157.27
4	1997.22	156.59
5 (Inlet WWTP)	5632.58	186.90

109 Table 1. Points examined in the water distribution network for the microturbine installation
 110 (Rodríguez-Pérez *et al.*, 2018)
 111

112 The existing installation is equipped with a multistream DN300 electrical regulating
 113 valve (Multinar) situated right at the inlet of the WWTP (Figure 2). The purpose of this
 114 valve is to reduce the flow which reaches it, and this descends from 220 l/s, when the

115 valve is open, to 120 l/s, which is the flow normally used in the installation. In this
116 procedure, the valve not only reduces the flow, but also limits the excessive energy
117 which comes with the water. It is this excess energy which will be used. When the
118 microturbine is installed, the water will reach the regulating valve with less force,
119 which will not create a problem provided that the energy dispelled in the miroturbine
120 is not greater than the excessive energy with which the water reaches the regulating
121 valve. This problem would not exist if the turbine is placed in a parallel position to the
122 regulating valve (in the WWTP).

123

124 Figure 2. Multistream DN300 electrical regulatory valve (Multinar), which controls the flow at the
125 inlet of the WWTP in 'Puebla de Guzmán' (Huelva, Spain) (on the left) and 'Cabeza del Pasto'
126 reservoir which channels water to the WWTP in 'Puebla de Guzmán' (Huelva, Spain) (on the right)
127

128 The 'Cabeza del Pasto' reservoir has a capacity of 140,000 m³ of water (Figure 2), and
129 serves as a storage and supply tank for the treatment station of potable water
130 (WWTP) in 'Puebla de Guzmán'. This reservoir was built only a few years ago, in the
131 year 2013, and it was constructed at the highest possible point. This was done so that
132 the water would reach the WWTP by gravitational force, making the use of additional
133 pumps unnecessary.

134 The 'Cabeza del Pasto' reservoir is supplied by four series of pumps which obtain
135 water from the Andévalo reservoir (Huelva). The individual capacity of each pump is

136 470 l/s with a height of supplied energy of 53 m. The framework of operation of this
137 pumping station depends on the amount of water supplied by the 'Cabeza del Pasto'
138 reservoir. When the level of water reaches the established minimum amount, the
139 pumping station starts to operate until the maximum capacity of the reservoir is
140 obtained.

141 The Andévalo reservoir has a capacity of 600 hm³, with the possibility of this being
142 increased to 1025 hm³. This fact makes it the reservoir with the greatest capacity in the
143 whole of the province of Huelva. It was built in 2003 and opened in 2004. It was
144 constructed to satisfy the great need for the pumping of water to the whole of the
145 Andévalo district (urban and irrigation uses).

146

147 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

148 **Alternative options for the installation of the microturbine**

149 When we decide to carry out our installation, it is necessary to follow several steps.
150 First of all, it is important to study where and how to install the microturbine. In other
151 words, at which point in the pipeline under study, and whether it should be placed in
152 a group or in a parallel position to the outline of the pipeline under study.

153 In order to obtain an optimum location of the microturbine, three factors need to be
154 taken into account: (a) Height: this should be the minimum possible, so that the water
155 pressure would be greater, in spite of gravity; (b) The distance between the selected
156 position and the outflow reservoir -this is due to the fact that, the greater the distance,
157 the greater the loss of pressure would be, due to friction with the pipe-; and (c) The net

158 jump that we have at each of the points, that is, the energy that reaches the studied
159 points less the need for water to reach the WWTP.

160 Therefore, the calculations that must be developed are: (a) To calculate the speed (V)
161 with which the water reaches the microturbine at any of the points to be studied; (b) To
162 obtain the real energy to be used at each of the points by microturbine applying the
163 energy conservation equation considering the loss of energy from friction.

164

165 **Selection of the microturbine type**

166 When the position of the installation has been decided, it is necessary to calculate the
167 speed with which the water fluid would reach the microturbine, in addition to its force.
168 In order to calculate the loss of energy to friction, the Hazen-Williams equation is used
169 because Daugherty and Franzini (1965) and Hwang and Hita (1987) suggest that this
170 equation is applicable for the flow of water in pipes larger than 5 cm and velocities less
171 than 3 m/s (Liou, 1998). These conditions are satisfied in the hydraulic installation
172 under study, as shown in the results section.

173 Having established the flow, power and speed with which the water reaches the
174 microturbine, the choice of type is made: turbine type (Pelton, Francis,...), the number
175 of nozzles in the turbine (one or several nozzles), and the number of pairs of poles of
176 the asynchronous generator (two, four, or six pairs). When these data are obtained, it is
177 possible to obtain the energy in MWh needed to supply the microturbine each year.

178 Once the yearly supply has been established, depending on the surplus energy
179 reaching the valve, a test will be made to determine whether it is necessary to install a
180 second microturbine, which will be installed in a series or in a parallel position.

181 The second installation option, as has been mentioned before, would be to place the
182 microturbine in a parallel position to the regulating valve. If this is done, the situation
183 of the microturbine would be the inlet of the WWTP. The difficulty incurred with
184 installing it in this position is the huge distance which exists between the outlet of the
185 reservoir and the height at which this point is situated. This is due to the fact that there
186 are other points at a lower level in the connection. What happens is that in the WWTP
187 the energy with which the water arrives is the net jump, which is inside the WWTP and
188 there is no need for an exit pressure at that point for an exit pressure at that point.

189

190 RESULTS

191 Optimum location of the microturbine

192 First of all, we calculate the speed (V) with which the water reaches the microturbine at
193 any of the points to be studied. Then we take into account the continuous flow (Q) for
194 the whole distance of 0.22 m³/s, and the diameter (D) for the length of the 500 mm pipe:

$$195 \quad Q = V \left(\frac{\pi D^2}{4} \right) \Rightarrow V = 1.12 \text{ m/s} \quad (1)$$

196 After this, we calculate each of the location points to be analyzed. With regard to
197 this, it should be taken into account that the reservoir is situated at a height of 236.40
198 m. Considering this, we will be able to calculate the difference in height regarding all
199 of the points. In order to calculate the losses to friction, the Hazen-Williams equation is

200 used (Daugherty and Franzini 1965; Hwang and Hita 1987; Liou 1998). Finally, with
201 the use of these calculations, it is possible to obtain the real energy contained at each of
202 the points.

203 The Hazen-Williams equation is:

$$204 \quad hf = 10.67 \left(\frac{Q}{C} \right)^{1.852} \frac{L}{D^{4.87}} \quad (2)$$

205 where Q = Flow rate (m³/s); L = Length of the pipe (m); D = inside hydraulic diameter
206 (m); and C = Hazen-Williams coefficient.

207 The pipeline is 5 years old. A life of 10 years is considered for the selection of the
208 Hazen-Williams coefficient C for pipes line because the turbine installation and
209 operation will begin like minimum two or three years after. For this reason the
210 coefficient of C=110 is chosen for pipes which are between 10 and 20 years old (Giles,
211 1962). This value is selected due to the fact that several years may pass before the
212 microturbine installation is made out.

213 This value of the Hazen-Williams C (C=110), obtained by table for ductil fundiction
214 with 10 years of life, has been verified using the approximation suggested by Liou
215 (1998) where C is related to the Reynolds number \Re , the relative roughness ε/D (in the
216 friction factor f via the Colebrook-White equation), the pipe diameter (D) and the
217 cinematic viscosity (ν) as:

$$218 \quad C = 14.07 f^{-0.54} \Re^{-0.08} D^{-0.01} \nu^{-0.08} \quad (3)$$

219 Considering a roughness of $\varepsilon=1$ mm, value quite common in aged pipes
220 (Christensen, 2000), the solution of equation (3) in the study case ($V = 1.12$ m/s and $D =$
221 0.5 m) is approximately 110. Therefore, the value of C=110 is a good approximation.

222 The calculations for the location point n° 1 (Figure 1) are:

223
$$\Delta H1 = 236.40 - 188.42 = 47.98 \text{ m} \quad (4)$$

224 where $\Delta H1$ is the difference of height between the outlet of the reservoir and point n° 1
 225 in m.

226 Losses of power $\Rightarrow h_f = 10.67 \left(\frac{0.220}{110}\right)^{1.852} \left(\frac{202.16}{0.5^{4.87}}\right) = 0.63 \text{ m} \quad (5)$

227
$$\Delta h1_{\text{final}} = 47.98 - 0.63 = 47.35 \text{ m} \quad (6)$$

228 where $\Delta h1$ final is the final difference of height after the losses of power have been
 229 eliminated at point n° 1 in m.

230 The calculation of the loss of energy to friction using the Darcy-Weisbach equation,
 231 considering a roughness of $\epsilon=1$ mm, gives similar results to those obtained with
 232 equation (5). In future works, it would be very interesting to estimate the Hazen-
 233 Williams coefficient C for pipe lines by measuring tracer concentrations by using the
 234 inverse method and to validate these values for a wide range of operational schemes
 235 (Al-Omari and Jamrah, 2005).

236 The results obtained in the other three points being studied can be observed in Table
 237 2. These calculations were obtained in the same manner as for point n° 1.

238

Point	ΔH (Difference of height between the outlet of the dam and the point where it is placed in m)	Losses of power (m)	Δh final (Final difference of height after the losses of power have been eliminated in m)
1	47.98	0.63	47.35
2	66.05	3.65	62.40
3	79.13	5.30	73.83
4	79.81	6.25	73.56
5 (inlet WWTP)	49.50	17.64	31.86

239 Table 2. Results obtained in the points studied for the installation of the microturbine
 240 (Rodríguez-Pérez *et al.*, 2018)

241 The real available energy that can be consumed by the turbine is the same at all
242 points of the installation (31.86 m at the entrance to the WWTP, Table 2), because if
243 more energy were consumed at an alternative point of the installation the water would
244 not have enough energy to reach the WWTP. For this reason, the only point that will be
245 studied finally is point 5 which is located at the inlet of the WWTP.

246

247 **Characteristics of the microturbine to be installed at the WWTP inlet**

248 Due to the requirements of flow and net jump of the studied device (0.22 m³/s and 32
249 m), the turbine recommended by the diagram of selection of hydraulic turbines
250 (flow/jump net) is the Francis type (Castellano, 2008). An asynchronous generator with
251 6 pairs (p) of terminals is used, for which the synchronism speed (n) is calculated as:

$$252 \quad n = 120 \frac{f}{p} \Rightarrow 120 \frac{50}{6} = 1000 \text{ rpm} \quad (7)$$

253 where f is the frequency of electric energy in Hz and n is 1000 rpm.

254 This way the calculation of the specific speed is as follows:

$$255 \quad P_{\text{WWTP}} = (0.87) \cdot 9810 \cdot (0.22) \cdot (31.86) = 59.82 \text{ kW} = 80 \text{ CV} \quad (8)$$

$$256 \quad N_s = n \cdot P_u^{1/2} \cdot H_n^{-5/4} = 1000 \cdot 80^{1/2} \cdot (31.86)^{-5/4} = 117 \text{ rpm} \quad (9)$$

257 with P_u = useful absorbed power and H_n = net height.

258 Therefore the energy generated by the microturbine would be:

$$259 \quad P = \gamma \cdot \eta \cdot Q \cdot H_n \quad (10)$$

260 where η is the yield from the microturbine in this case will be 0.87 (87%); γ is the
261 specific weight = water density \times gravity = $1000 \text{ kg/m}^3 \times 9.81 \text{ m/s}^2 = 9810 \text{ N/m}^3$.

262 Since the microturbine would be working an average of 14 hours a day during the
263 whole year, the total amount of energy it would generate for the year would be:

$$264 \quad \text{Energy} = \text{hours per year} \times P \quad (11)$$

$$265 \quad \text{Hours per year} = 14 \text{ hours} \times 365 \text{ days} = 5110 \text{ hours} \quad (12)$$

$$266 \quad \text{Energy per year for the WWTP} = 5110.58454 = 298.70 \text{ MWh per year} \quad (13)$$

267 The Francis turbine type depends on N_s , in our case for N_s we have a Francis
268 medium turbine, N_s is between 110 rpm and 200 rpm [Low speed Francis ($N_s < 110$),
269 medium Speed Francis ($110 < N_s < 200$), fast speed Francis ($200 < N_s$)].

270 According to the results obtained, the ideal microturbine to be installed would be
271 the following:

272 - A medium speed Francis turbine.

273 - Raw height (H_b) = 49.50 m

274 - Net height (H_n): 31.86 m

275 - Flow (Q): $0.22 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$

276 - Specific speed of the turbine (N_s): 117 rpm

277 - Power: $59.82 \text{ kW} = 80 \text{ CV}$

278 - Estimated number of hours of workload: 14 hours per day, 5110 hours per year

279 - Energy: $59.82 \text{ kW} \times 5110 \text{ h} = 305.68 \text{ MWh per year}$

280 - An asynchronous generator with six pairs of terminals at 1000 rpm

281

282 **Installation budget**

283 With the corresponding data to the hydraulic installation at study, in Table 3 is shown
 284 the approached investment costs proportioned by some sector companies.

285

Technical Parameters			
Net Head:	Hr	32	m
Flow Rate:	Q	0.22	m ³ /s
Capacity:	P	60	kW
Turbine		Generator	
Model	F246-26	Model	SF60-4/22
Rated rotating speed r	1000 rpm	Rated Efficiency of Generator η _f	91%
Efficiency of turbine η _f	87%	Efficiency of the generator f	50Hz
Rated Discharge Q _r	0.22 m ³ /s	Rated voltage of generator V	400 V
		Rated rotating speed r	1000 rpm
Product Price			
Name of Commodity	(pcs)	Euros	
Turbine: F246-26	1	11500	400V, 50Hz
Generator: SF60-4/224	1	3400	
Excitation Device: BKF- 60kW	1	2170	
Governor: ST-100	1	1080	
Valve: Z45T-10-DN350	1	1350	
Packing fee	1	1000	
Total amount		20500	

286 Table 3. Budget the turbine + Excitation Device + Generator + Packing fee + Valve

287

288 On the other hand we have the cost of assembly and installation, which we estimate
 289 at € 19500. Which would mean a total cost of € 40000.

290 To calculate the annual energy generated, it is necessary to take into account the
 291 efficiency of the generator, which is 91% since we only took into account the efficiency
 292 of the turbine:

293 Energy: $59.82 \text{ kW} \times 5110 \text{ h} \times 0.91 = 278.17 \text{ MWh per year}$ (14)

294 This equates to more than € 20,000 per year, which means that the investment has
295 recovered in 2 years. With the requirements of flow and net height of the hydraulic
296 network in study, a Pelton turbine was also evaluated but the total costs were higher
297 than with the Francis turbine with a recovery period of this investment of 5 years
298 (Rodríguez-Pérez *et al.*, 2018).

299

300 DISCUSSION

301 This study have as main objective the evaluation of the viability of the insertion of a
302 microturbine in a pressure network of water supply. The results show that the amount
303 of usable energy is significant. The microturbine chosen is the Francis type, due to the
304 fact that it is the one which possesses greater efficiency for this water flow. As has been
305 observed, the characteristics of the microturbine vary, depending on the point chosen
306 for its insertion. More exactly, what varies is the number of pairs and revolutions per
307 minute at which the microturbine works.

308 One of the most important aspects of the study is the insertion of the microturbine,
309 in our case, the WWTP inlet has been chosen. When the position has been decided, it
310 was necessary to determine how to insert the microturbine, whether in a series or in a
311 parallel position with the pressure reducing valve (Figure 3). In this regard, the latter
312 alternative was chosen. This consists of placing the microturbine in a parallel position
313 (with the installation of a by-pass) to the pressure reducing valve if the position chosen
314 were the inlet of the WWTP (Figure 3a).

315 The final decision to place the microturbine in the WWTP inlet is that at the exit of
316 the turbine we do not need the water to come out with a certain force and therefore we

317 can take advantage of all the energy that reaches it. Therefore, at the input of the
318 WWTP the water derived from 'Cabeza del Pasto' reservoir is distributed to a
319 treatment pond with height sufficient to run the water through of the all WWTP.

320

321 Figure 3. Diagram showing the installation of the microturbine at the inlet of the WWTP: (a)
322 parallel position (with the installation of a by-pass) to the pressure reducing valve and (b) series
323 position to the pressure reducing valve
324

325 This means that the most adequate position for generation is not ideal one due to
326 inadequate pressure to reach the WWTP. The position chosen is to place it in a parallel
327 position to the regulating valve which is situated at the inlet of the WWTP. Thus the
328 problem is avoided but energy generated would be less. The results obtained for the
329 annual energy generation are less than in the ideal position. However in order to
330 calculate the installation, the most unfavorable data have been used. This guarantees
331 that obtaining the annual energy calculated is assured and this could possibly increase.

332 Having made the necessary calculations for its placement, medium speed Francis
333 turbine and an asynchronous generation with six terminals functioning at 1000 rpm has
334 been selected for the position.

335

336 CONCLUSIONS

337 This paper shows how effective the insertion of a microturbine in a hydraulic network
338 can be, and how energy can be generated by a renewable source. This type of
339 installation has been studied with great interest in the last few years, since it could be
340 an ideal for many urban and irrigation water distribution systems. This generated
341 energy could be add directly to the electricity network but perhaps the best option
342 would be to use it as self-consumption in the water distribution network (for example,
343 for the energy requirements in control devices such as motorized valves, for the
344 illumination of the WWTP, etc.).

345 In this particular case in study, the best alternative is the insertion of a microturbine
346 in a parallel position with a regulating valve at the inlet of the WWTP. Some rather
347 interesting results have been obtained due to the large flow available, and it has been
348 possible to compensate losses from friction due to the long distance covered by the
349 water between the reservoir and the WWTP. The reason for this is the huge difference
350 in height which exists between the reservoir, from which the flow facts, and the point
351 where the microturbine is to be placed.

352 This paper presents an approach for technicians and managers of water distribution
353 systems who, with a good knowledge of the operating schemes of their hydraulic

354 network, are aware of the significant contribution of energy that could be achieved at
355 certain points with the installation of a microturbine. In order to quantify this energy
356 potential in certain locations of water distribution networks, with complex operation
357 schemes that depend on the time of day and month of the year, this work could be
358 useful as a methodological guide for the optimum location of microturbines and for the
359 selection of the type of microturbines to be install.

360

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366

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